

Significance of Calcium Chloride and Sodium Silicate in Adsorption of Pure Water

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ABSTRACT

Water resources are the cornerstone of human survival and development, but in recent years, their quality has been seriously threatened. Traditional water purification techniques, such as the use of alum or activated carbon, are effective but have potential risks, such as excessive ingestion of aluminium ions. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the adsorption capacity of calcium chloride, activated carbon, sodium silicate and alum to pigment molecules and harmful ions in water under different environmental conditions. Through experiments simulating the sedimentation tank of a water purification plant, we found that the mixture of calcium chloride and sodium silicate performed well in removing pigment molecules and reducing water turbidity, with removal rates as high as 96% and 95.9%, respectively. The results show that the mixture of calcium chloride and sodium silicate has great potential in the field of wastewater treatment.

Keywords: *calcium chloride, water pollution, sodium silicate, water purification, activated carbon*

1. INTRODUCTION

Water is an important resource for human survival, but it has been gradually polluted in recent years. Wastewater from homes and buildings often contains pollutants, heavy metals, and pathogens. Globally, approximately 380 billion cubic meters of wastewater is produced every year. Only about 55% of this water is properly treated, leaving behind a large amount of untreated environmental wastewater. If this water is not properly treated, it will have serious repercussions for the population and society. Public health, soil quality, etc., will be negatively affected.

Some of the strategies available are being used to solve this problem. Traditional wastewater treatment plants generally use three steps to purify the wastewater: initial static

sedimentation, biological treatment of toxic gas chlorine, and chemical flocculation of alum. This method is expensive to process and requires a large area of land.

Activated charcoal is a very good water purifier, but it cannot remove water pathogens. Alum is a very widely used flocculant, but it can cause excessive levels of aluminium in water. The search for a new suitable water purifier is imminent. In a serendipitous discovery, I found that when calcium chloride and sodium silicate are mixed in wastewater, the water becomes clear after a period of time. Moreover, I couldn't find much related explanation online, which suggests that calcium chloride and sodium silicate may possess a special water purification method that has not been given much attention. Calcium chloride is inexpensive and widely used, but it is mainly used as a desiccant by using its good water absorption. Sodium silicate is also inexpensive, but it is mainly used in the construction industry. The purpose of this study is to find new water purifiers by evaluating the efficiency of various water purification agents and by performing different tests on the physicochemical properties of water.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1.1 Reagent materials

- 500g pure anhydrous calcium chloride (from Tianjin Zhonglian)
- 500g pure sodium metasilicate nonahydrate (all sodium silicates in the text are nonahydrate) (from Tianjin Zhonglian)
- 500g pure anhydrous potassium aluminum sulfate (alum) (from Tianjin Zhonglian)
- 500g glycerol (from Tianjin Zhonglian)
- 1L Wahaha Pure Water (the conductivity of the test sample reached 1.56)
- 5L muddy river water containing sediment (collected from the Huai River)

2.1.2 Indicators and equipment

pH test strips, burettes, EDTA solution, zirconia, methylene blue, copper sulfate, sink, etc¹

2.2 Brief steps

First of all, the water intake tank or large beaker simulates the sedimentation tank of the water purification plant, and each group is isolated in the same environment and each group is operated at the same time

¹ Non-major equipment is not listed here.

Next, the reagents were added sequentially in groups (A. sodium silicate group, B. calcium chloride group, C. activated carbon group, D. calcium chloride mixed with sodium silicate, E. mixed group, and alum group of equal mass).²

Observe and wait.

Observe and record the time required for each dispersion system to become colorless and transparent

The physicochemical parameters of the original dispersion system were tested

When the turbidity and pigment are not visible to the naked eye, the supernatant is taken and its physicochemical parameters (pH, turbidity, hardness, etc.) are tested

Estimate the efficiency first, fill it in form 2 Adsorption rate of each substance

2.3 Physical and chemical analysis

The physicochemical analysis of wastewater is essential to assess the quality of treated and raw water. Physical parameters, such as pH, turbidity, and hardness, provide insight into the acidity/alkalinity of the water, suspended solids, and calcium and magnesium content. In addition, chemical parameters such as fluoride content were analyzed to determine the presence of contaminants and to assess the usability of the method.

2.3.1 pH

Take a pH test strip

Dip the pH test strip in the water sample

Allow it to dry and compare the color to the pH color chart

2.3.2 Turbidity

Place a plain piece of white paper on the floor

Install the turbidity meter about 8 cm above the ground

Look through the upper end of the opening of the turbidity tube to make sure you can see the black cross at the bottom of the turbidity tube

Slowly pour the water sample into the tube while observing the black cross

Stop pouring when the cross is no longer visible

The turbidity value is measured according to the markings on the turbidity tube

2.3.3 Hardness

Take a 5 mL water sample

Add 1-2 drops of ammonia buffer to raise the pH to 10

Add a small amount of Eriochrome powder

² The data required for each group are shown in the table below

Add EDTA solution to the burette.

Titrate until the color changes from burgundy to blue

Calculation Method: EDTA mL * 400 = Hardness (mg/L) used in titration

2.3.4 Fluoride

Take a 50mL water sample

Add 2.5 mL of zirconia

Pour the solution into another tube and mix

Allow the solution to develop for 1 hour

Compare the color to the fluoride content color comparison card and record the value of the matching color.

2.4 Data processing and analysis

Change the ambient temperature and humidity, repeat the above experimental steps many times, calculate the average value of each group of data, and organize the average value of the experimental data form 3. Physical and chemical properties of water after purification.

	parameter	Observations	Acceptable range
1	pH	6.4	6.5-8.5
2	turbidity	145	6-11
3	fluoride	3.0	1-1.5
6	hardness	800	300-600

form 1 Physical and chemical properties of the original river water

	water	Sodium silicate solution	glycerol	ethanol	Glycerol + sodium silicate	Ethanol + sodium silicate	Murky river waters
calcium chloride	++	+++++	+	-	+++	+++	++
alum	+	+	-	+	-	+	+
activated carbon	+++	+++	++	+++	++	+++	+++
sodium silicate	-	/	-	-	/	/	+

form 2 Adsorption rate of each substance³

	A. Sodium silicate group	B. Calcium chloride group	C. Activated carbon group	D. Calcium chloride mixed with sodium silicate	E. Alum group	Acceptable range
pH	8	7	7.5	8	10	6.5-8.4
turbidity	16	18	8	6	8	6-11
fluoride	0.8	0.9	1.2	0.7	1.0	1-1.5
hardness	450	650	570	500	480	300-600

form 3 Physicochemical properties of water after purification

3. DISCUSSION

From the data in the above three tables, it can be seen that the adsorption rate and removal ability of calcium chloride or sodium silicate alone are not high. However, when the

³ Represents relative rates only and is used for qualitative analysis.

two are mixed, they exhibit excellent water purification capabilities. Consult the data and analyze it to find important information:

- A. The hydroxide hydrolysis of calcium ions and silicates in calcium chloride can effectively adsorb water phosphate and reduce the risk of water eutrophication. (Guan et al., 2012, 3)
- B. Silicate ions can react with heavy metal ions in wastewater to form silicate precipitates
- C. After calcium chloride is dissolved in water, chloride ions have a sterilizing and disinfection effect, which can remove microorganisms in water
- D. Calcium ions can adsorb metal cations or pigment molecules in water and immobilize them at the bottom (Figure 1.3) to help filter impurities from the water.
- E. Sodium silicate is alkaline when dissolved in water, which can be used to adjust the pH of water
- F. Further tests on calcium chloride and sodium silicate found that when the two were mixed with clean water, they emitted a strong fishy smell, and due to limited conditions, it was not possible to further explore the cause of the odor. It is speculated that it may be the taste of poly-sinking ferric ions. Therefore, when using the two to mix clean water, a certain proportion of activated carbon should be added for odor adsorption, and the best mass ratio at 15 °C was 6:3:1 (sodium silicate pentahydrate: anhydrous calcium chloride: activated carbon) after repeated tests
- G. Interestingly, calcium chloride in sodium silicate solution turns into something like a "stalactite" Figure 1.1 of substances, extending from the bottom to the surface of the water. After the addition of absolute ethanol, white flocculent appeared next to the "stalactite column". Figure 1.2 . Both have a certain ornamental value.

FIGURE 1.1 "STALACTITE" SHAPED

- H. In the environment of glycerol, the water purification capacity of various water purifiers decreased (form 2 Adsorption rate of each substance), presumably related to its viscosity. Calcium chloride adsorbs glycerol firmly to the bottom of the beaker.
- I. In the environment of ethanol, the ability of calcium chloride to adsorb pigments is seriously inhibited (Figure 1.2), the addition of sodium silicate relieves partial inhibition.

FIGURE 1.2 CALCIUM CHLORIDE IN ETHANOL

- J. Calcium chloride can not only participate in water purification, but also obtain fresh water directly from the air. Fresh water is obtained from air using mechanical compression/condensation and adsorption methods, which are efficient, low energy consumption, environmentally friendly, low cost and renewable. Compared with other adsorbents, The reusability of CaCl_2 -based chemical sorbents can effectively reduce the total cost of practical application of adsorbents. (Zhang et al., 2016, 2)
- K. Calcium silicate hydrate (CSH) is a porous medium with nano- to micro-sized gel pores and capillary pores that are important for intermolecular adsorption. (Yang et al., 2016, 1)
- L. The novel material, consisting of calcium chloride incorporated into an alginate-derived matrix, can be widely used in solar-powered extraction of water from the air. Calcium chloride is able to absorb its own weight More than 95% water, known as one of the most promising salts. (Paul & Michael, 2018, 2)
- M. Alum water purification may cause excessive levels of aluminum ions in the water, which is toxic to plants and may cause Alzheimer's disease in humans.

- N. Alum water purification looks clearer at the same quality, only because the mixed group contains activated carbon, and in fact the mixed group has a higher heavy metal removal rate. As Figure 1.2

FIGURE 1.3 CALCIUM CHLORIDE FIRMLY ADSORBS PIGMENTS

FIGURE 1.4 ALUM GROUP (LEFT) MIXED GROUP (RIGHT)

4. CONCLUSION

Calcium chloride and sodium silicate play a huge role in water purification, which can effectively remove suspended solids, fluoride, phosphate, pathogens, etc. in water. In addition, the purified supernatant can quickly remove most of the residual calcium ions and microorganisms after boiling, and soften the water again, which is harmless to the human body and conducive to human absorption compared with alum.

The mixed powder of sodium silicate pentahydrate, anhydrous calcium chloride and activated carbon with a mass ratio of 6:3:1 has excellent water purification ability, (because sodium silicate can improve the ability of calcium chloride to adsorb pigments, and calcium chloride can improve the ability of sodium silicate to coalesce and settle in the future), which will have broad application prospects in the future.

Compared with alum, calcium chloride can not only purify water resources but also absorb water resources directly from the air, which has a significant role in the recycling of global water resources and can alleviate problems such as water shortage.

In the future, the widespread application of this method may alleviate the acute water scarcity in Africa. Hopefully, future research can confirm this.

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